

Insurance Financial Risks And Their Impact On The Benefits Of Dar Al Salam And Al Hamra Insurance Company

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 05, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 07, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Risks, Revenues, Benefits, Insurance, Financial, Return</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5484438</p>	<p><i>The study dealt with a topic that is no less important than contemporary financial ideas, which is the impact of financial risks faced by insurance companies that affect returns, because each of the SAS activities is a trade-off between return and risk, and the aim of the study are indicators of return measurement, risk and analysis as well as investment returns, measurement and analysis Financial for insurance companies listed in the Iraq Stock Exchange to know the role of risks and their impact on revenues and that its goal is to show the relationship and the degree of impact of risks on both investment returns and total returns</i></p>

Introduction

Since ancient times, individuals, their properties and projects have been exposed to various risks that may cause financial losses, material losses, and others, which have natural risks, that is, no one can prevent their realization, and they cannot bear the consequences on their own. If they are realized, then the need for individuals to find ways to avoid such losses, including insurance, is based on the distribution of risk or harm to a group of individuals rather than to the individual who was at risk. And through the activity of the insurance company to cover risks, because it has a large cash balance by receiving insurance premiums from the insured, and holders of insurance policies for rights, and works with insurance to cover the company's losses and pay compensation to the insured when the check is exposed to risk. In order not to freeze and maintain a cash balance, the insurance company resorts to investing in the areas it deems appropriate, to achieve financial returns that contribute to strengthening its financial position and thus increasing its ability to reduce costs for the purpose of insurance deduction. Insurance premiums, which increases the competitive strength of the insurance company compared to competing companies.

First: the problem of the study

The insurance sector faces major challenges in doing business through the risks it is exposed to and taking appropriate measures to avoid them and maintaining a competitive position by entering into investments that achieve an appropriate return compared to the risks to which it is exposed. A problem in the study can be summarized as follows

- What are the risks to Dar Salaam and Al Hamra Insurance Company?
- What are the returns of Dar Al Salam and Al Hamra Insurance Company?
- What is the impact of risks on the returns of Dar Al Salam and Al Hamra Insurance's investments?

Second, the importance of the study

The importance of the study highlights the importance of the insurance sector, which is one of the important financial sectors and its impact on the economy, where insurance companies provide an element of safety for all economic sectors and thus achieve economic development, as well as the entry of insurance companies into important investments that support the economy

The message consists of two dimensions

- The theoretical dimension, which includes clarification of the concepts of insurance, risk, return and investment to reach a homogeneous intellectual perspective of the impact of risks on the returns of insurance companies, which contributes to enriching the scientific library with topics that were and still are. Mission.
- The applied dimension, which represents an attempt to diagnose the dimensions of risks to which insurance companies are exposed to returns and which will be applied in the insurance sector.

Fourth: Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are as follows The research comes to shed light on an important sector of finance, but it is an insurance sector, as it focuses on providing a theoretical framework that helps to understand the important foundations and rules that are being built and based on the concept of risks and returns. in the insurance sector. In order to clarify the role of this concept in ensuring the stability of the institution and supporting continuity and development in a turbulent environment, and then analyzing this concept for companies working in this field instead of analyzing their investments. In order to get a feel of how to manage the different types of risks that may be encountered in the course of production, I have mandated outlining the different methods and procedures that have been followed in its efforts to control and control the risks. To which he is subjected. Find out what if risk management is an effective and important functional function in the insurance sector service objectives

Fifth: Academic assignments

The study was launched in order to find a solution to its main problem from three main hypotheses, and a number of sub-hypotheses emerged from these two hypotheses- :

The first main hypothesis: There is a statistically significant relationship between risks and financial investment returns the study sample companies emerged from two sub-hypotheses of these hypotheses as follows- :

1. There is an archaeological relationship with statistical and moral significance between the risks and returns of the financial investments of Dar Al Salam Insurance Company.
2. There is a statistically significant and ethical impact relationship between the risks and the total returns of Dar Al Salam Insurance Company.

The second main hypothesis: There is a statistically significant archaeological relationship between the total risks and returns of the study sample companies, and two sub-hypotheses emerged from these hypotheses as follows :

1. There is a statistically significant and ethical impact on the relationship between the risks and returns of the financial investments of Al Hamra Insurance Company.
2. There is a statistically significant and significant impact relationship between the risks and the total returns of Al Hamra Insurance Company.

The third hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect of risks on the returns of financial investments and the total returns of the study sample companies.

Insurance

First, the definition of insurance

There are several definitions of insurance that differ among themselves according to the picture in which the writer is interested in the subject of insurance, including- :

1. The language of insurance: It is derived from the word safety, which indicates peace of mind and the removal of fear. It is said: The security of the homeland that reassures its people, and the security of the evil one are safe, and so-and-so is in such-and-such, and trusts him, and reassures him, or makes him trust him. {And they cooperated in that. Righteousness and piety, and do not cooperate in sin and aggression” (Surat Al-Ma’idah, verse 2) and the Almighty’s saying: {And hold fast to the rope of God. And do not swear” (Al-Imran, verse 103). And in the Sunnah of the Messenger, may God’s prayers and peace be upon him and his family and companions, the believer was a solid building for the believer that strengthens one another (Judges, 2011: 1)
2. Economic definition of insurance: insurance aims to form a body or association in which members contribute, to insure losses that one of its members may incur.
3. Legal considerations, the fact that the reader (the prospective customer) is interested in knowing the insurance contract, and according to these rights the obligations of the contract, and that the concerned informs the insured of the nature of the contract and the basis governing it. It regulates the contract relationship and obligations between the insured and the insured throughout the term of the insurance contract. It extends to doing some of these principles before entering into this contract. Most of our insurance studies are based on Article 983 of the Iraqi Civil Code. (Pink.2016: 75) Insurance also defines the following: A system or method intended to protect organizations and individuals from damage to potential physical risks if risks are insured, by shifting the burden of risk to the insurance company, which undertakes compensation. The losses of the insured or the beneficiary for all or some of the Saudi items that have been realized. On the other hand, the insured shall calculate the insurance premiums in periodic installments according to the mathematical and statistical bases mentioned in the concluded insurance contract (Hakimah 47: 2014).

Second: the effects of insurance

1-Economic effects: The economic impact of insurance lies in

1. Facilitating access to funds for the implementation of projects Insurance reduces the burden of hedging risk through a contingency reserve fund that entrepreneurs turn to in the absence of insurance.
2. Insurance provides high levels of security for owners of capital

3. The role of insurance in facilitating international trade
4. Insurance works to spread awareness, prevent losses and reduce their effects
5. The developing country obtaining hard currency in return for the compensation due for the risks reinsured abroad through reinsurance. (Kamal, 2014: 19)

2-Social influences

As for the higher social security: it works to address many desperate social problems, ailments, disease and unemployment, and brings comfort, tranquility and calm among the members of society. The goal is human and social by preserving individuals, their property and wealth from various accidents (Kamel, 2016: 93)

Third: The characteristics of the insurance contract

An insurance contract has many characteristics, including:

1. mutual insurance contract
2. insurance contract, netting contract
3. Emergency insurance contract c bypass
4. The insurance contract is a binding contract for both sides
5. The insurance contract is a permanent contract
6. Obligation insurance contract
7. The insurance contract is a named contract (Beljoudi, 2015: 16)

Fourth: Insurance companies

Insurance companies play the role of the regulator by gathering the largest possible number of parties exposed to risk who want to obtain insurance services, and to meet the services for them, and therefore the insurance companies represent the so-called insured (the insured) (Ahmed, 2016: 420) that can be defined as: A financial institution that collects money from the insured, then reinvest them directly or indirectly, thus contributing to financing and providing the financial needs of various business activities, as you know: Insurance and reinsurance companies are companies that conclude and implement insurance and reinsurance contracts in accordance with the legislation in force. By definition, it is clear to us that insurance companies operate within a legal framework and that their activity is based on providing safety to the insured by compensating losses. (Jalal and Salma, 2013: 26)

Fifth: Insurance risks

The risk from the point of view of the insurance company is the difference between the expected losses on the basis of which the amount of the net insurance premium was calculated and the amount of actual losses that the insurance company is obligated to compensate. Policyholders who have suffered from accidents of insured risks, and therefore the risk from the point of view of the insurance company is: the opposite between actual losses and the deviation of expected losses, and describing the loss from the insurance company's point of view is the increase. Actual losses of expected losses can be at the general level of the company's business in a particular insurance or in a group of branches, and not at the level of a particular incident, from the definition of loss for the insurance company that has: the deviation that occurred as a result of the discrepancy between the expected values and the realized values that actually occurred.

Analyze investments, returns, and risks for a trap sample

First: Analyzing the investments and returns of Dar Al Salam Insurance Company

It is clear from Table No. (1) that the investment amount of Dar Al Salam Insurance Company in 2005 amounted to (1384938387) dinars, and decreased in 2006 and amounted to (1187265582) dinars, with a growth rate of (-14.27%) compared to (-14.27%). The previous year, which was the highest decrease in the growth rate of the company's investment amount during the study period, then increased in 2007 and was (1983408567) dinars with a growth rate of (67.06%), which is the highest. The growth rate of the volume of investments during the study period and continued to rise in 2008 amounted to (249,9082593) dinars with a growth rate of 26%, and increased in 2009 and amounted to (2800,887239) dinars with growth. By (12.08%), to increase the volume of investment in 2019 by a smaller percentage (7142405140) dinars and a growth rate of (27.63%), which is the highest amount of investment during the study period. The investment returns of Dar Al Salam Insurance Company were also volatile, as in 2005 the return on investment amounted to (172964431) dinars and achieved a percentage of (1.28) of the total returns of the company, then the return on investment decreased in 2006 to (54130595) dinars, which is the lowest return on the investments of a company Dar AlSalaam. As for the insurance during the study period, with a declining growth rate (-68.70%), which is the highest declining growth rate in investment returns during the study period, with a rate of (0.32) of the total returns, to rise thereafter in 2007. And achieving (194872744) dinars with a growth rate of (260%), which is The highest growth rate in the investment returns of Dar Al Salam Company during the study period at a rate of (1.06) of the total returns, and an improvement in the continuous returns in 2018 and achieved a return of (209404781) dinars, with a growth rate of (10.86%) and a rate of (6.41) of the total returns, which is the highest percentage during The study period, and in 2019, achieved a decline of (27285333) dinars, with a growth rate of (30.30%) and a rate of (1.68) of the total returns. As for the total returns of Dar Al Salam Insurance Company in 2005, it amounted to (135324943) dinars and increased in 2006 AD. It amounted to (171103062) dinars, and the total

return continued to increase in the following years until the year 2014 reached a total return of (390570899) dinars, which is the highest comprehensive return amount for Dar Al Salam Insurance Company during the study period, and it decreased after 2015 and reached (281698787) dinars, and it continued to The decline in the years that followed until 2018 reached (32,692,63) 5) Dinars, which is the lowest total return for Dar Al Salam insurance during the study period and improved after 2019 and amounted to (162374033) Dinars. As for the ratio of investment return to the total returns of Dar Al Salam Insurance Company. The company was in 2018 (641%) which is the highest percentage during the study period due to the increase in the amount of compensation. In 2019 the ratio was (168%) and in 2014 the ratio was (29%) which is the lowest ratio of return on investment to the total returns of Dar Al Salaam Insurance during the study period.

Return the ratio of investment to total return	Total return growth rate	Amounts in Iraqi dinars*	Investment return growth rate	Investment returns	Investment growth rate	Investments	the year
		returns the college					
1.28		135,324,943	--	172,964,431	--	1,384,938,387	2005
0.32	0.26	171,103,062	(68.70)	54,130,595	(14:27)	1,187,265,582	2006
1.06	0.07	183,437,661	260.00	194,872,744	67.06	1,983,408,567	2007
0.48	0.36	248,943,598	(39.16)	118,563,253	26.00	2,499,082,593	2008
0.63	(0.00)	248,869,802	32.49	157,090,374	12.08	2,800,887,239	2009
0.93	0.02	252,633,688	50.25	236,036,079	7.95	3,023,586,764	2010
1.20	0.04	262,866,985	33.73	315,652,602	6.25	3,212,422,748	2011
0.82	0.07	280,113,658	(26.91)	230,721,636	16.43	3,740,066,168	2012
0.37	0.30	362,986,020	(41.01)	136,108,238	13.84	4,257,649,644	2013
0.29	0.08	390,570,899	(18.06)	111,524,678	15.96	4,937,126,560	2014
0.34	(0.28)	281,698,787	(15.15)	94,626,218	2.62	5,066,499,374	2015
1.36	(0.51)	137,696,857	97.25	186,653,037	(9.57)	4,581,562,310	2016
2.49	(0.45)	75,945,323	1.20	188,894,165	(10.70)	4,091,303,528	2017
6.41	(0.57)	32,692,635	10.86	209,404,781	36.78	5,596,027,023	2018
1.68	3.97	162,374,033	30.30	272,853,330	27.63	7,142,405,140	2019

Table(1)investment amounts T returns to Dar Al Salam Insurance for the period 2005 to 2019

Source: Prepared by the researcher with the approval of the final accounts of the company

Second: - Analysis of the investments and returns of Al-Hamra Insurance Company

It is clear from Table No. (2) that the investment amount of Al-Hamra Insurance Company in 2007 amounted to (737,028169) dinars, and thus the volume of investment increased in 2016 to reach (3,700,467,454) dinars, with a growth rate of (16.37%), and the increase continued in 2017 and the volume of investment (5252149273) dinars with a growth rate of (41.93)%, which achieved the highest growth rate during the study period, then increased in 2018 the amount of investment (6929077013) dinars. With a growth rate of (31.93)%, but in 2019 the investment volume amounted to (6945989713) dinars, with a growth rate of (0.24%), which is the lowest growth rate during the study period. As for the investment returns of Al Hamra Insurance Company, they were also volatile, reaching in 2007 (47364096) dinars, at a rate of (0.37) of the total returns, and in 2018 it achieved a return of (259986122) dinars and a growth rate of (211.82)%, which is the largest growth rate of investment returns during the study period at a rate of (0.36) of the total returns, but in 2019 it achieved a return of (30026129) dinars and a growth rate. By (-88.45%), which is the largest decrease in the growth rate of investment returns during the study period by (0.04) of the total returns. The total revenue of the Red Insurance Company in 2005 amounted to (12.111 million) dinars, the lowest total return of the Red Insurance Company during the study period, which rose after 2006 and amounted to (17.984 million) dinars and continued to rise until 2008 and amounted to (673). (200721) dinars dipped later in the year 2009 and achieves a total return of

(334662276) dinars and increased in 2011 and reached (1329861438) dinars, which is the highest total return of the Hamra Insurance Company during the study period. , and decreased in the following years until 2014 and amounted to (409202065) dinars, and improved in 2015 and reached (867287444) dinars, and continued to improve in 2018 and amounted to (72, 7055261) dinars, and then declined in 2019 and. An amount of (685,770457) dinars. As for the ratio of investment returns to the total returns of Al Hamra Insurance Company, it was in 2007 (37%), which is the highest percentage achieved during the study period, and in 2018 it was lower (36%) and this is to direct the company's investments towards good investments that achieve a good return.

Table (2) Investment amounts and returns for the Red Insurance Company for the period 2005-2019

Amounts in Iraqi dinars*							the year
Return the ratio of investment to total return	Total return growth rate	total returns	Investment return growth rate	Investment returns	Investment growth rate	Investments	
-	-	12,111,000	-	-	-	-	2005
-	0.48	17,984,000	-	-	-	-	2006
0.37	6.18	129,213,972	-	47,364,096	-	737,028,169	2007
0.11	4.21	673,200,721	51.52	71,766,975	93.88	1,428,926,476	2008
0.19	(0.50)	334,662,276	(10.48)	64,247,944	51.80	2,169,168,287	2009
0.07	0.00	335,814,468	(63.53)	23,433,177	26.90	2,752,711,372	2010
0.03	2.96	1,329,861,438	79.39	42,037,421	(8.07)	2,530,674,219	2011
0.04	(0.10)	1,202,192,849	1.47	42,653,544	22.38	3,096,987,521	2012
0.06	0.02	1,227,536,798	60.76	68,570,539	1.36	3,139,232,227	2013
0.06	(0.67)	409,202,065	(64.92)	24,055,525	0.64	3,159,255,636	2014
0.07	1.12	867,287,444	168.75	64,649,818	0.65	3,179,797,854	2015
0.12	(0.45)	479,717,139	(11.53)	57,197,833	16.37	3,700,467,454	2016
0.13	0.35	648,291,150	45.77	83,375,833	41.93	5,252,149,273	2017
0.36	0.12	727,055,261	211.82	259,986,122	31.93	6,929,077,013	2018
0.04	(0.06)	685,770,457	(88.45)	30,026,129	0.24	6,945,989,713	2019

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the final accounts of the company

Third: the risks of insurance companies

Dar Al Salam Insurance Company risk analysis

It was distinguished from Table No. (3) the risks that Dar Al Salam Insurance Company was exposed to, which had a difference, which was the effect of the change in the amount of return on investment, as it reached the highest risk ratio in 2018 that amounted to (0.0073), and the company recorded a return of (0.01) dollars, and in In 2006, the risks were lower, reaching (0.0016) and the company achieved a return of (0.13), while the lowest amount of risks was in 2015 when it amounted to (0.0001), and the company recorded a return of (0.08) dollars. It is clear that the relationship between risk and negative return for a company Dar es Salaam during the study period due to the company's directives, its investments are high risk investments and do not generate a suitable component. In addition to the increase in compensation and expenses

Table (3) Amount of return and risk for Dar Al Salam Insurance Company

a company Dar AISalaam		the year
$(R_t - \bar{R})^2$	Return on total investment	
0.0004	0.11	2005
0.0016	0.13	2006
0.0013	0.13	2007

0.0011	0.12	2008
0.0011	0.12	2009
0.0005	0.11	2010
0.0003	0.11	2011
0.0006	0.12	2012
0.0011	0.13	2013
0.0009	0.12	2014
0.0001	0.08	2015
0.0028	0.04	2016
0.0049	0.02	2017
0.0073	0.01	2018
0.0047	0.02	2019

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the final accounts of the company

Al Hamra Insurance Company's risk analysis

J was distinguished from Table No. (4) by the risk difference suffered by Red Insurance Company as a result of the change in the amount of return on investment, as it reached the highest level of risk in 2008 amounting to (0.6466) and the company recorded a return of US\$. (1.12) the highest investment return achieved in the Red Insurance Company during the study period, and this confirms the positive relationship between returns and risks during the study period, and the Red Insurance Company notes the continuation of the relationship during the years of study. In 2011 the amount of risk was (0.3234) and the company recorded a return of (0.89), and in 2006 the amount of risk was (0.0829) and the company recorded a return of (0.03) in 2012. Less than (0.0802) the company recorded a return of (0.60) dollars, In 2005, the risks were lower and amounted to (0.0770) and the company recorded a return of (0.04), which is the lowest return for the red insurance check. a company. During the study period, the risks decreased in 2013, reaching (0.0083), and the company achieved a return of (0.41)

Table (4) Amount of return and risk for Al Hamra Insurance Company

a company red		the year
$(R_t - \bar{R})^2$	Return on total investment	
0.0770	0.04	2005
0.0829	0.03	2006
0.0105	0.22	2007
0.6466	1.12	2008
0.0575	0.56	2009
0.0088	0.22	2010
0.3234	0.89	2011
.0802	0.60	2012
0.0083	0.41	2013
0.0557	0.08	2014
.0209	0.17	2015
0.0493	0.10	2016
0.0354	0.13	2017
0.0458	0.10	2018
0.0484	0.10	2019

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the final accounts of the company

The impact of insurance risks on the returns of insurance companies, research sample

First: Test the first main hypothesis

In this paragraph, the first main hypothesis of the study is through the statistical tool, which is the tested paired samples test (double samples test), based on the data shown in Table No. (5) That were obtained and discussed in the previous paragraphs of this. After analyzing the data shown in the previous table, a number of results were reached, as shown later in Table (6)

Table (5) Returns and risks of financial investments for insurance companies, research sample for the period 2005-2019

a company Dar AISalaam		a company red		the year
$(R_t - \bar{R})^2$	The rate of return on financial investments	$(R_t - \bar{R})^2$	The rate of return on financial investments	
0.0004	0.12	0.0770	-	2005
0.0016	0.05	0.0829	-	2006
0.0013	0.10	0.0105	0.06	2007
0.0011	0.05	0.6466	0.05	2008

0.0011	0.06	0.0575	0.03	2009
0.0005	0.08	0.0088	0.01	2010
0.0003	0.10	0.3234	0.02	2011
0.0006	0.06	.0802	0.01	2012
0.0011	0.03	0.0083	0.02	2013
0.0009	0.02	0.0557	0.01	2014
0.0001	0.02	.0209	0.02	2015
0.0028	0.04	0.0493	0.02	2016
0.0049	0.05	0.0354	0.02	2017
0.0073	0.04	0.0458	0.04	2018
0.0047	0.04	0.0484	0.00	2019

Source :Prepared by the researcher and based on the final accounts of the research sample companies

Table(6)Testing the first sub -hypothesis of the first main hypothesis

Paired Samples Test									
	Paired Differences					T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Final statistical decision
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference					
				Lower	Upper				
X ₁ - y ₁	.08271	.16301	.04209	-.00756-	.17298	1.965	14	.070	Hypothesis rejected

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS program.

The first sub-hypothesis and specifically the value of (Sig = 0.070) in Table (6), the first alternative hypothesis of the first main hypothesis was rejected. H 1) which states that ((there is a statistically significant effect relationship between the risk and returns of the financial investments of Dar Al Salam Insurance Company)), because the value of (Sig >), and therefore the acceptance of the first null hypothesis (h 0), which indicates that there is no significant effect Statistical significance of the relationship between the risks and returns of the financial investments of Dar Al Salam Insurance Company.

Table No. (7) To test the second hypothesis of the first main hypothesis

Paired Samples Test									
	Paired Differences					T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Final statistical decision
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference					
				Lower	Upper				
X ₂ - y ₂	-.00712-	.04269	.01102	-.03076-	.01652	-.646-	14	.529	Hypothesis rejected

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the program SPSS.

As for the second hypothesis, specifically the value of (Sig = 0.529) in Table No. (7), the alternative second sub-hypothesis of the first main hypothesis (H1) was rejected, which states that ((there is statistical significance. Impact) of the relationship between risks and returns on the financial investments of a company Hamra Insurance), because the value of (Sig > 0.05), thus accepting the second null hypothesis (H 0), which indicates that there is no statistically significant relationship. Between the risks and returns of the financial investments of Al-Hamra Insurance Company.

Second: In this paragraph, the discussion of the second main hypothesis of the study is analyzed based on the data shown in the following table (8), and through the use of the double sample statistical tool (dual sample test (within the test) Comparison of means The data were analyzed to obtain the results shown in the following tables (8-12)

Table (8) total returns and risks of insurance companies, sample of the research, for the period 2005-2019

a company Dar AISalaam		a company red		the year
$(R_t - \bar{R})^2$	Return on total investment	$(R_t - \bar{R})^2$	Return on total investment	
0.0004	0.11	0.0770	0.04	2005
0.0016	0.13	0.0829	0.03	2006
0.0013	0.13	0.0105	0.22	2007
0.0011	0.12	0.6466	1.12	2008
0.0011	0.12	0.0575	0.56	2009

0.0005	0.11	0.0088	0.22	2010
0.0003	0.11	0.3234	0.89	2011
0.0006	0.12	.0802	0.60	2012
0.0011	0.13	0.0083	0.41	2013
0.0009	0.12	0.0557	0.08	2014
0.0001	0.08	.0209	0.17	2015
0.0028	0.04	0.0493	0.10	2016
0.0049	0.02	0.0354	0.13	2017
0.0073	0.01	0.0458	0.10	2018
0.0047	0.02	0.0484	0.10	2019

Source: Prepared by the researcher and based on the final accounts of the companies

Table :(9) Testing the first sub -hypothesis of the second main hypothesis

Paired Samples Test									Final statistical decision
	Paired Differences					T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference					
				Lower	Upper				
$x_1 - y_{21}$	-.21462-	.21891	.05652	-.33585-	-.09339-	-3.797-	14	.002	Hypothesis accepted

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the program SPSS.

As for the first sub-hypothesis , specifically the value of $\text{Sig} = 0.002$ in the table(9 , (It is accepting the hypothesis sub - first alternative of the second main hypothesis) H_1 (which states that)) there is a statistically significant effect relationship between the risk and the total returns of the Dar Al Salam Insurance Company ,(because the value of) Sig , ($0.05 >$ thus rejecting the first null hypothesis) H_0 (which indicates that there is no statistically significant impact relationship between the risk and the returns of the financial investments of Dar Al Salam Insurance Company.

Table(10)Testing the second sub -hypothesis of the second main hypothesis

Paired Samples Test									Final statistical decision
	Paired Differences					T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference					
				Lower	Upper				
$x_2 - y_{22}$	.04621	.04574	.01181	.02088	.07154	3.913	14	.002	Hypothesis accepted

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS program.

As for the second hypothesis, specifically the value of ($\text{Sig} = 0.002$) in Table (10), it rejected the second sub-hypothesis of the main hypothesis II (H_1), which states that ((there is no statistically significant effect). between risk and total returns of the insurance company red relationship), because the value of ($\text{Sig} > 0.05$), thus accepting the second null hypothesis (H_0), indicating that there is no statistically significant effect relationship between risk and total. Al Hamra Insurance Company returns.

Third: Testing the third hypothesis using the statistical tool (ANOVA), analysis of variance, analysis of variance Table (11) to test the third hypothesis

ANOVA ^a							Final statistical decision
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.		
1	Regression	.013	2	.007	13.478	.001 ^b	Hypothesis accepted
	Residual	.006	12	.000			
	Total	.019	14				
a. Dependent Variable: Y2, Y1							
b. Predictors: (Constant), X							

Through the results of Table (11), specifically the value of ($\text{Sig} = 0.001$), the third alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted, which states that ((there is no statistically significant relationship with the risk returns on financial investments and the total returns of the study sample companies)), because the value of ($\text{Sig} < 0.05$), thus

rejecting the third null hypothesis (H₀), indicating that there was no statistically significant effect of risk on the returns of financial investments and the total returns of the study sample. Comp.

Table (12) Summary of the Study

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.832 ^a	.692	.641	.02216

Through the results of Table (12) it is clear that the study clarified the value (69%) according to the value of R Square.

Table (13) coefficient analysis of the third main hypothesis

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.042	.022		1.921	.079
	X1	-1.033-	.506	-.482-	-2.042-	.064
	X2	.454	.096	1.119	4.738	.000

Through the results shown in Table (13) (for the analysis of the coefficients of the study variables, the regression equation can be formulated as follows- :

$$Y = 0.042 - 1.033 X1 + 0.454 X2 + e$$

It is clear that the financial risk (X1) inverse relationship with the returns of financial investments (y1) where the change (increase) by one unit of financial risk is offset by a change (decrease) by (1.033) in the investment returns due to direct the money of some insurance companies to investments that generate returns Inversely with the risks, and the investments of some insurance companies were negatively affected when the risks increased, as it was found that the financial risks (X1 (positive relationship with total insurance returns)) companies (y1) where the change (increase) of financial risks by one unit corresponds to the change (increase) in Mekda's total revenue increased by (0.454)

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

1. Insurance has an effective role in economic and social life because it is the best way to protect individuals and their property, as it provides them with a protection cover when they are exposed to danger, by giving them financial compensation and then preserving the purchase. The power of individuals within the economy, as well as transferring the various types of risks that institutions may be exposed to other companies, namely, reinsurance companies.
2. The results of the financial analysis showed that Dar Al Salam Insurance Company achieved the highest return on financial investments during the study period, followed by Al Hamra Insurance Company.
3. The results of the financial analysis of the total returns showed that Al Hamra Insurance Company achieved the highest total return during the study period, followed by Dar Al Salam Insurance Company.
4. Al-Hamra Company achieves the highest level of risk and at the same time achieves the highest total return, and this indicates that the relationship is direct between return and risk, the higher the risk, the higher the return.
5. The results of the statistical analysis showed a significant relationship and a positive effect between the financial risks and the returns of the financial investments of insurance companies, and this is consistent with the hypothesis of the study.

Recommendations

1. The necessity of spreading insurance awareness in the social community, which allows knowing the importance of insurance in daily life by enhancing trust between individuals and insurance companies.
2. Follow up the insurance market and competitors and maintain the market share by diversifying the insurance services provided by insurance companies in proportion to the needs of customers.
3. The necessity of having a control system aimed at evaluating the company's performance on the basis of sound scientific methods and tools aimed at reducing risks.
4. Paying attention to risk management through building and developing specialized risk management departments in insurance companies.
5. Seeking the assistance of advisory institutions and experts in drawing up the components of the investment portfolio to achieve the appropriate return.

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